

WEBINAR – 27 March 2025 – 14:00–15:30 CET

Navigating Digital Democracy: Challenges and Future Directions

POST-EVENT REPORT

The webinar *Navigating Digital Democracy: Challenges and Future Directions*, co-organised by the Horizon Europe projects *INNOVADE*, *AI4Deliberation*, and *PERYCLES*, was held on March 27th as a timely reflection on how technology is reshaping democratic processes across Europe. Bringing together over 100 participants from academia, civil society, local government, EU institutions, and the tech sector, the event examined the risks and opportunities presented by digital transformation in democratic life.

The three projects are funded under **HORIZON-CL2-2024-DEMOCRACY-01-07 - Digital democracy**

INNOVAD (Innovative Democracy through Digitalisation)

- Duration:** 3 years (Jan 2025 – Dec 2027)
- Consortium:** 11 partners led by Beyond the Horizon
- Scope:** Transforming digital democracy through comprehensive technological and social solutions
- Key Objectives:**
 - ☑ Build an interdisciplinary knowledge base on digital democracy
 - ☑ Develop a “Digital Democracy App” with robust data protection
 - ☑ Provide toolkits for decision-makers to advance digital democracy

AI4Deliberation

Artificial Intelligence for Institutionalised, Multimodal, Gamified, Mass Democratic Deliberations

- Duration:** 3 years (Nov 2024 – Oct 2027)
- Consortium:** 11 partners led by UNI SYSTEMS
- Scope:** Developing ethical AI tools to enhance democratic processes and institutional trust
- Key Objectives:**
 - ☑ Create AI-powered tools for assessing and implementing deliberative processes
 - ☑ Address challenges of political polarisation and citizen disengagement
 - ☑ Conduct four large-scale pilot studies on critical topics like climate change

PERYCLES

Participatory Democracy that Scales

- Duration:** 3 years (Jan 2025 – Dec 2027)
- Consortium:** 10 partners led by University of Groningen
- Scope:** Interdisciplinary research project developing evidence-based methods for digital democracy technology
- Key Objectives:**
 - ☑ Create principled assessment methods for digital democracy solutions
 - ☑ Develop open-source implementations of democratic participation platforms
 - ☑ Generate a comprehensive library of best practices for online participation

191 registrants from 46 countries

TOP 5 countries:

- ☑ Belgium (26)
- ☑ Germany (23)
- ☑ UK (14)
- ☑ Italy (11)
- ☑ France (10)

Organisation type:

The session opened with remarks from **Pierre di Giacomo** from the *European Commission's DG Justice*, presenting the emerging contours of the European Democracy Shield, a new strategic initiative designed to **counteract disinformation, foreign interference, and other systemic threats to democratic integrity in the EU**. The presentation highlighted the increasing importance of algorithmic accountability, transparency in online political communication, and the need to protect the digital public sphere from manipulation and exclusion. This policy backdrop provided a strong context for the rest of the discussion, where the emphasis shifted from institutional frameworks to applied solutions and community-based innovation.

The governance perspective was introduced by **Berten Kempen**, a representative from the *City of Geel*, one of the two pilot municipalities in the INNOVADE project. Speaking from direct experience, he emphasised the need to treat public participation as a process of co-creation rather than a box-ticking exercise. While digital tools offer new channels for involving citizens in policymaking, these mechanisms **must be designed to close the feedback loop**. If citizens do not see the result of their engagement, trust in public institutions can erode quickly.

The societal and civic tech angle was presented by **Andreas Nitsche** from *LiquidFeedback*, a decision-making software for civics and politics and the developers of the PERYCLES platform. Andreas underscored the need to build systems that both enable meaningful participation and resist manipulation. In a fragmented and often polarised online environment, the role of well-structured, secure digital democratic infrastructure has become more critical than ever. The perspective also highlighted how **deliberative processes can help rebuild common ground**, especially when paired with decision-making tools that reflect transparent procedures and a commitment to fairness.

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The coordinators from the three Horizon Europe projects then presented their respective approaches to digital democracy innovation. **Fatih Yilmaz** from *INNOVADE* introduced its Digital Democracy App, which is being co-developed and tested with communities in Belgium and Spain. The app will be built around key principles such as GDPR compliance, user-centred design, and transparency in AI-driven processes. **Efthimios Tambouris** from *AI4Deliberation* presented its modular, open-source AI components designed to support structured, ethical deliberation within existing digital participation platforms. Rather than creating new tools from scratch, the project aims to enhance existing systems through responsible integration. **Davide Grossi** from *PERYCLES* concluded the research segment by focusing on the challenge of scale versus quality in public engagement. The project seeks to reconcile the need for broad participation with the importance of deliberative depth by applying interdisciplinary insights from political science, AI, and social psychology.

Throughout the event, there was a shared recognition that digital democracy is not simply a technical issue but a deeply social and political one. The rise of disinformation, the growing influence of platform monopolies, and persistent digital divides all contribute to a context in which democratic participation cannot be taken for granted. At the same time, there was clear consensus that with the right frameworks, tools, and collaborative approaches, **digital technologies can still be harnessed** to improve inclusivity, transparency, and trust in democratic systems.

The webinar served as both a milestone and a launchpad. As the three projects move forward with research, co-creation, and policy engagement, they will continue to collaborate closely and share knowledge across their respective networks. The event also marked the beginning of an open dialogue with external stakeholders, many of whom have since expressed interest in joining future workshops, policy roundtables, and pilot activities. A stakeholder mapping form remains available on the INNOVADE website for those interested in contributing to the ongoing work of the projects.

The full recording is available online, together with the slides.

[Recording Link](#)

[Slides Link](#)

The organisers hope to support a broader European effort to ensure that the digital transformation of democracy is not just secure and ethical but also participatory and inclusive.